

DIGITAL INFORMATION AS A MEANINGFUL ELEMENT OF DIGITAL INDUSTRY COMPONENTS

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Abstract. The article deals with the concept of digital information as an integral content element of individual components of the Smart Industry. The establishment of digital information becomes necessary in the framework of the detection and investigation of cybercrime (including cyber attacks of industrial enterprises). The authors analyze the concept of digital information and point out the lack of its legislative consolidation. It is noted that the text containing various personal or corporate information can act as digital information. If this information is important for establishing the fact of a cyberattack of an enterprise, the circumstances of a criminal, administrative, civil or arbitration case, it will act as an object of forensic research and be expressed in a digital footprint. Special attention is paid to the analysis of the properties of digital information, which made it possible to identify its features: representation in digital form; mediated by a material carrier; the ability to be transformed (recoded) and copied; collected, investigated and used only with the help of special technical means. In the course of studying digital information, it is important to take into account not only the type and properties of the information itself, but also the features of its material carrier. It is concluded that the quality of a particular material carrier can directly affect the security of digital information, access to it at all stages of the study.

Keywords: digital information, digital footprint, Smart Industry, signs of digital information, investigation of cyber attacks, digital information carriers.

The industrial revolution has a consequence of the global digitalization of most areas of human activity and constant transformations in the field of information technology. This gives great opportunities in the development and transformation of the economy, education, social sphere, medicine, industry and various areas of scientific activity. The downside of this development is the presence of threats in the digital information space. One of the most acute problems of law enforcement is the identification and investigation of cybercrimes committed using digital technologies, which is largely explained by the complexity of identifying digital traces and establishing its informational content.

The concept of "digital information" is a generic concept in relation to "computer information", since it describes all the variety of forms in which information used by modern computing, telecommunications and other technical devices can exist and be transmitted. As digital information, depending on the type of crime committed and the specifics of the digital footprint, text can act – information about age, ethnicity, racial gender, social affiliation, citizenship, social status, interests and habits, health, relationships, geolocation, etc., graphic images, photographic images, video recordings, audio recordings, etc. If this information is relevant for establishing the fact of a cyberattack of an enterprise, circumstances in a criminal, administrative, civil or arbitration case, it will act as an object of forensic research. In this case, it is not the external form and way of perceiving information that is important, but the way of its existence, expressed in its consolidation through digital technologies in the digital footprint. Digital information is information converted into a digital code. It is recorded by means of digital recording, with the help of which the signals recorded on the carrier are converted into a sequence of code (digital) combinations of pulses (signals). Information is also transmitted by

means of signals, which, unlike a message, are an external structure of information intended for transmission [3, p. 55]. This ensures high quality, which means the reliability of the reproduced signals. The information available for use by various technical devices (computers, smartphones, telephones, routers, household appliances connected to the Internet, etc.) must be digital and transmitted in a network environment. The network environment includes environments in which direct data transmission takes place (cables, connectors, network cards, air transmission medium). Digital information can be transmitted by various types of signals by nature: electrical signals (in the case of data transmission via a copper cable); light pulses (in the case of using fiber optic cables); radio waves (using wireless devices). At the same time, digital information recorded on digital drives can exist in the form of mechanical signals and only in the process of reading through the use of special technical devices goes into digital form. Digital information is data displayed in a digital form suitable for recognition, processing or storage using a computer or information system, existing in the form of files, transmissions, logs, metadata or network data. Digital information, being one of the forms of information and an object of cognition and research, must have certain properties. In particular, attributive, pragmatic and dynamic properties of information are distinguished in computer science [3, pp. 24-25]. So, attribute properties

–these are properties without which information does not exist. These include–

- the continuity of information from the physical medium; - the linguistic nature of information;

- discreteness of information. The information contained in the information is discrete, that is, it characterizes individual factual data, patterns and properties of the studied objects, which are distributed in the form of various messages;

- continuity. Information tends to merge with the information already recorded and accumulated earlier, which contributes to the progressive development and accumulation. At the same time, pragmatic properties characterize the degree of usefulness of information for the consumer and manifest themselves in the process of its use. This category includes:

- the meaning and novelty of information, which characterizes the movement of information in social communications and highlights the part of it that is new to the consumer;

- usefulness of information

- a property aimed at reducing the uncertainty of information about an object;

- the value of information. It is determined by the significance of information for consumers and users;

- cumulative information. Characterizes the accumulation and storage of information–

- completeness of information

- sufficiency of data for making decisions or creating new data based on existing ones.

- reliability of information

-the property of information to be correctly perceived. Data occurs at the time of signal registration, but not all signals are useful

– there is always some level of extraneous signals. If the useful signal is registered more clearly than extraneous signals, the reliability of the information is considered high.

- adequacy of information

is the degree of compliance with the real objective state of the case; - availability of information

- the ability to obtain this or that information;
- relevance of information
- the degree of compliance of information with the current moment of time;
- objectivity and subjectivity of information. The objectivity of information

is relative, since the methods are subjective [3, p. 25; 4, p.7]. The dynamic properties of information characterize its change over time. These include: the growth of information, which means the movement of information in information communications, its constant multiple dissemination or repeatability; aging of information, that is, its exposure to the influence of time. Relying on the properties described above, it is possible to identify specific features of digital information as an object of forensic research:

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